

Effect of Cationic and Non-ionic Surfactants upon the Acidic Hydrolysis of *N*-Benzylbenzohydroxamic Acid

KALLOL K. GHOSH* and SANTOSH K. SAR

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010

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The hydrolysis of hydroxamic acid is of considerable interest and importance, both from a chemical point of view, and because of its relevance in biological and biochemical processes¹. In recent years, molecular organised assemblies, viz. micelles, microemulsions, vesicles, etc. have emerged as attractive reaction media for investigating the reactivity, selectivity and catalysis of a number of chemical and biochemical reaction². However, micellar effects upon acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of hydroxamic acids have been much less explored³.

In the present communication, we report a systematic study of the cationic micelles of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, C₁₆H₃₃N⁺Me₃Br⁻) and cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC, C₁₆H₃₃H⁺C₅H₅Cl⁻) and non-ionic micelles of polyoxyethylene (23) lauryl ether (Brij-35, C₁₂H₂₅(OCH₂CH₂)₂₃OH) and polyoxyethylene (10) diisobutylphenol (Triton-X, C₁₄H₂₁(OCH₂CH₂CH₂)₁₀OH) on the hydrolysis of *N*-benzylbenzohydroxamic acid (BBHA) in 10% (v/v) dioxane-water medium under acidic condition (0.87 M HCl).

Results and Discussion

The acid hydrolysis of BBHA is first order with respect to the substrate and to the acid concentration. The observed pseudo-first order rate constant (k_w) values for the reaction in surfactant solution of CTAB, CPC, SDS, TX-100 and Brij-35 are given in Table 1. At fixed concentration of HCl (0.87 M) and BBHA, the first order rate constants decrease with increasing [surfactant]. The acid-catalysed hydrolysis of BBHA follows the A-Ac₂ mechanism⁴ with rate-determining attack of water on the protonated BBHA (Scheme 1),

Scheme 1

The hydrolysis mechanism in the micellar environment depends upon two factor : (i) the orientation of the substrate molecule in the micellar pseudophase and (ii) the relative stabilisation or destabilisation of transition state

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR ACIDIC HYDROLYSIS OF BBHA IN SURFACTANTS*

10 ³ [Surfactant] <i>M</i>	10 ⁵ k_w (s ⁻¹)			
	CTAB	CPC	Brij-35	TX-100
0.0	12.3	12.3	12.3	12.3
0.05	—	—	11.1	—
0.10	—	—	11.3	—
0.52	—	—	—	—
0.69	12.3	—	—	—
1.39	10.4	12.3	11.9	10.7
9.60	7.62	10.6	9.65	9.50
15.0	7.01	8.70	7.14	9.48
24.6	5.99	7.40	6.57	8.67
48.5	4.75	4.60	6.16	6.08
58.7	3.18	3.80	5.45	4.84

*At 65°, 0.87 M HCl, medium : 10% (v/v) dioxane-water.

by the micelles relative to in the bulk phase. Basically rate effects can be attributed to electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions between the micelles and reactants. The electrostatic surface potential at the micellar surface can attract or repel ionic species, and a strong hydrophobic interaction can bring about the incorporation into micelles even if reagents that bear the same charge as ionic micelles. In 0.87 M HCl, BBHA is very less protonated and this process will be opposed by the electrostatic repulsions between two cations. The partitioning of H⁺ between micelles and bulk phase will shift the protonation equilibrium to the left (Scheme 1) due to decreased concentration of H⁺ in the Stern layer and to the stabilisation of the unprotonated form of the substrate by the CTAB micelles.

Quantitative treatments of rates : Micellar effects upon reaction rates have been analysed by Menger and Portnoy⁵ and Piszkiwicz⁶ models. The overall reactions are illustrated in the Scheme 2. The substrate will be distributed between the aqueous (W) and micellar (M) pseudophases.

Scheme 2

In this scheme, D_n represents micellized surfactant whose concentration is given by the total surfactant concentration D less that of the monomeric surfactant, i.e. $[D_n] = [D] - \text{cmc}$. (The critical concentration, cmc, is taken as the concentration of monomeric surfactant). K_s represents substrate binding constant and k_w and k_M represent first order rate constants for the reaction in the aqueous and micellar pseudo phases respectively. This model leads to the relationship,

$$1/(k_w - k_\psi) = 1/(k_w - k_M) + 1 \{ (k_w - k_M)K_s[D] - \text{cmc} \} \quad (1)$$

By plotting $1/(k_w - k_\psi)$ against $1/([D] - \text{cmc})$ it is possible to calculate k_M and K_s (Table 2). The cmc values of CTAB and CPC were determined conductometrically and values

TABLE 2—FITTING PARAMETERS : PORTNOY AND MENDER PSEUDO-PHASE MODEL

Surfactant	CMC M	D_T range $10^{-3} M$	K_s	Corr. coeff.
CTAB	1.20×10^{-3}	9.60–98.7	105.5	0.977
CPC	9.00×10^{-4}	15.0–98.7	49.3	0.997
Brij-35	6.0×10^{-5a}	1.39–98.7	32.5	0.999
TX-100	5.7×10^{-4a}	9.6–48.5	21.4	0.973

^aFrom Ref. 7.

for TX-100 and Brij-35 taken from literature⁷. Comparison of rate constants (Table 1) in $1.39 \times 10^{-3} M$ surfactants shows that CTAB inhibits the hydrolysis 1.2 times, CPC 1.0, Brij-35 1.3 times and TX-100 1.3 times. Several factors, such as the adsorption of the substrate in the Stern layer of the micelles, effective micellar charge, and water structure are important for micellar catalysis. BBHA can be preferably solubilised in the Stern layer zone of the micellar surface. The kinetic effect of the non-ionic surfactant is lower than that of CTAB and CPC. If the substrate were buried deeply in the interior of the micelle, it would be protected from H^+ , and therefore we conclude that any substrate which is incorporated into micelles of the non-ionic surfactant must be in a water-rich region close to the surface of the micelle. The decrease in the rate of the bimolecular reactions with surfactants can be treated by Piskiewicz model⁶,

$$\log \frac{(k_\psi - k_w)}{(k_M - k_\psi)} = n \log [D] - \log K_D$$

According to equation (2), a plot of $\log (k_\psi - k_w)/(k_M - k_\psi)$ vs $\log [D]$ for a micellar reaction is linear with a slope n . Fairly linear correlations are observed and the values of cooperativity index (n) and $\log [D]_{50}$ derived therefrom are given in Table 3. In micellar-inhibited reactions, as most of the reactions take place in the bulk aqueous phase, the rate constant for the reaction on the micellar phase (k_M) is nearly zero, $\log [D]_{50}$ value represents the concentration

TABLE 3—FITTING PARAMETERS : PISKIEWICZ MODEL

Surfactant	n	$\log [D]_{50}$	$10^3 K_D$	Corr. coeff.
CTAB	1.837	-2.68	23.2	0.997
CPC	0.924	-1.60	48.9	0.977
Brij-35	0.415	-131	196	0.999
TX-100	0.403	-1.48	402	0.986

of surfactant required for half-maximal catalysis or inhibition of reaction. A value of n greater than unity implies positive cooperativity, i.e. the binding of a first molecule of a substrate to the surfactant molecule makes it easier for subsequent molecules to bind; a value less than unity would indicate a negative cooperativity, i.e. the first molecule bound makes it more difficult for the next one to bind. The n value now obtained ranges from 0.40 to 0.90. $[D]_{50}$ is also in good agreement with the experimental observation. Values of K_D (Table 3) indicate the existence of significant surfactant-substrate interactions in all cases analysed. This suggests that it is more appropriate to view n as representing average stoichiometry of the surfactant-substrate aggregate.

Temperature effect : Activation parameters were obtained by a least squares method using a computer programme (Eyring equation). Activation parameters are listed in Table 4. These are in favour of bimolecular mechanism⁸. Nearly equal ΔG^\ddagger values for the reactions in absence and in presence of micelles confirm that the reaction mechanism is same in both the media. Addition of micelles of the CPC, Brij-35 and TX-100 leads to a decrease in the entropy because of unfavourable electrostatic incorporation.

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF BBHA*

Parameters	No surfactant	CTAB	CPC	Brij-35	TX-100
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	73.5	77.0	63.9	69.3	69.9
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	104.5	105.0	103.8	104.0	104.1
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-105.0	-94.0	-134	-117	-115
Corr. coeff.	0.997	0.998	0.947	0.998	0.998

*Surfactant concentration = $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Experimental

BBHA was prepared by a standard method⁹. The acid used was of A.R. grade. Dioxane (AnalaR) was used as such. Ferric chloride solution used in the spectrophotometric procedure was prepared by dissolution of anhydrous ferric chloride (S.M., L.R.; 44 g) in distilled water (1 dm³) containing concentrated HCl (10 ml). CTAB (E. Merck), CPC, Brij-35 and TX-100 (all Loba) were used as such.

Kinetics were followed spectrophotometrically by measuring the concentration of the hydroxamic acid by the colour reaction with Fe^{III} ions. An aliquot of the reaction

mixture (2 ml) was periodically removed and added to ferric chloride (2 ml), the resulting solution diluted to 10 ml and its absorbance measured with a Systronics 108 spectrophotometer. Beer's law is obeyed by the system. Least-squares analysis was carried out on Wipro 386 computer under MS-DOS.

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